

The Effect of Psychosocial Rehabilitation on Perceived Stigma among Patients with Schizophrenia in Kelantan, Malaysia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Schizophrenia is a chronic mental illness which is highly related with stigma and discrimination. Sociodemographic and clinical factors are among the predictive factors of perceived stigma. Psychosocial rehabilitation plays a role in reducing the perceived stigma among patients with schizophrenia.

Objectives: This study is aimed to compare the perceived stigma level in patients with schizophrenia who attended psychosocial rehabilitation with patients who did not attend psychosocial rehabilitation in Kelantan and its predictive factors.

Designs: A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted between two groups of schizophrenia patients who received psychosocial rehabilitation and those who did not.

Materials and Methods: The Devaluation-Discrimination Scale (DDS) Malay Version self-report questionnaire was completed by 70 participants in each group. All participants (n = 140) also were rated by interviewer with the Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale-Extended version (BPRS-E).

Results: The mean score of perceived stigma in schizophrenia patients who attended psychosocial rehabilitation was 2.40 (SD = 0.39) and in those who did not attend was 2.73 (SD = 0.39). The mean difference score of perceived stigma between the two groups was .335 (95% CI .204, .465) with p value < 0.001. Simple linear regression was used to explore the predictive factors for stigma in patients with schizophrenia. The variables with p-value < 0.25 or clinically important were selected for multivariable analysis. Multiple linear regression was proceeded and revealed that the significant predictive factors were ethnic (p < .005), somatic concern (p < .05) and depression (p < .001).

Conclusions: Ethnic, somatic concern and depression were the significant predictive factors for stigma in schizophrenia patients. Psychosocial rehabilitation significantly reduced the perceived stigma among patients with schizophrenia. Thus, patients with schizophrenia should receive psychosocial rehabilitation and the predictive factors should be considered as part of the holistic management of schizophrenia towards recovery.

KEY WORDS

perceived stigma, psychosocial rehabilitation, schizophrenia

INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia impairs the cognitive, behaviour and function of the affected individuals. This chronic mental illness is highly related with stigma and discrimination resulted in a significant burden to caregivers and people suffering from schizophrenia. Moderate or high levels of perceived discrimination were reported in 69.4% of individuals with schizophrenia¹⁾. Patients suffering anxiety, depression, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) and schizophrenia showed that 43.6% of them had moderate to high self-stigma²⁾.

It is vital to know the predictive factors of perceived stigma in mental illness and several studies have a closer look at them. Lower incomes and unemployment associated with devaluation and discrimination³⁾. However, some studies showed that higher educational level and socio-economic status were associated with more perceived stigma⁴⁾. Parents occupational level also revealed that the higher the level, the greater the experience of discrimination³⁾. Nevertheless, in the same study, those who believed that their earnings were insufficient for their basic needs showed more feelings of rejection and interpersonal stigma⁵⁾.

Apart from that, the factor of psychopathology severity in schizo-

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Table 1. Sociodemographic Character of All Schizophrenia Patients (n = 140)

Variable	All schizophrenia patients (n = 140)	
	Mean (SD)	Frequency (%)
Age	18 and above	37.95 (10.79)
Gender	Male	79 (56.4)
	Female	61(43.6)
Ethnicity	Malay	138(98.6)
	Chinese	1(0.7)
	India	1(0.7)
Marital status	Single	105(75)
	Married	23(16.4)
	Divorcee/Widow	12(8.6)
Education level	Primary school	14 (10)
	Secondary school	97(69.3)
	Tertiary	29(20.7)
Occupation	Not working/Housewife	98(70)
	Unprofessional workers	38(27.1)
	Professional workers	4(2.9)
Level of income	< RM600	58(41.4)
	RM600 to RM1500	60(42.9)
	> RM1500	22(15.7)
Duration of diagnosis	< one year	13(9.3)
	≥ one year	127(90.7)

phrenia was studied in perceived stigma. Severity of illness in schizophrenia was positively associated with the level of perceived stigma⁶. People with more severe psychopathology symptoms and lesser social skills yield more negative responds⁷. Depression and demoralization also associated with stigma⁸. Looking at hospital setting factor, patients at a state hospital had lower perceptions of mental illness stigma than those hospitalized in a community ssetting⁹.

The importance of studying stigma in mental illness is because of the negative impact of it. Stigma and discrimination cause significant burden to both the individuals with mental illness and to their family members. Stigma and discrimination also have been associated with poor quality of life, low self-esteem and social withdrawal in people with schizophrenia¹⁰.

Internalized stigma might cause people with mental illness to accept the disbelieving prejudice against them thus lose their self-esteem. This might lead to feelings of shame, a sense of alienation and social withdrawal¹¹. On top of that, internalized stigma was also related to poor adherence with psychosocial¹² and pharmacological treatment^{1,13}, reduced quality of life¹⁴, and general functioning^{2,15}.

In other studies, self-stigma was related to negative psychosocial and clinical outcomes, including reduced hope, low self-esteem, diminished quality of life and poor treatment adherence^{2,11}. One local study in Kelantan, Malaysia found that those with high level of self-esteem were associated with low perceived stigma¹⁶.

Thus, it really reflects that self-stigma and self-esteem exhibited the strongest contributions to psychosocial treatment adherence¹². This adherence will fasten patients to achieve a recovery. Therefore, interventions are needed to reduce stigma in order to help the patients to have better recovery. Several studies had been looked at the effect of psychosocial interventions in reducing self or perceived stigma among schizophrenia patients.

Hence, involvement of patients in rehabilitation decreased self-stigma; and this correlated with surge in self-esteem among them¹⁷. A ran-

domized-control trial (RCT) that studied a nine-week psycho-educational intervention in Maryland also showed there was a reduced of internalized stigma among psychosocial rehabilitation patient¹⁸. Besides that, participants in a RCT study reported increased self-confidence after a feasible ten-sessions recovery-oriented group intervention¹⁹. Another study of a twelve-sessions of stigma focused cognitive therapy also showed an improvement of internalised shame, hopelessness and self-rated recovery²⁰.

In India, a one-year randomized study looked at a community-based intervention that included psychoeducation, adherence management strategies, health promotion, rehabilitation and steps to deal with stigma and discrimination. It showed significant positive association with stigma and caregivers burden²¹.

Pertaining to Malaysia mental health policy, psychosocial rehabilitation interventions are the important elements of schizophrenia management²². These rehabilitations are available in hospital, primary healthcare center and community mental health centre (CMHC). As in Mental Health Act 2001, CMHC is a centre for comprehensive community care treatment of persons with mental disorders which includes rehabilitation²³.

There were limited data or research on effect of psychosocial rehabilitation on perceived stigma among schizophrenia patients in Malaysia. Therefore, the aim of this study was to compare the perceived stigma level in patients with schizophrenia who attended psychosocial rehabilitation in Kelantan with patients who did not attend psychosocial rehabilitation and its predictive factors.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

Participants with diagnosis of schizophrenia according to DSM-5 and age more than 18 years old were selected from psychosocial rehabilitation centers in Kelantan by using simple random sampling technique. Seventy participants who attended psychosocial rehabilitation and consented were recruited into the case group. Another group of seventy patients with schizophrenia who attended outpatient clinic in respective center but did not attend psychosocial rehabilitation were included in a control group. A comparative cross-sectional study between the two groups of schizophrenia patients was conducted from January till September 2017.

The ethical clearance was attained from Human Research Ethics Committee, Universiti Sains Malaysia (JEPeM Code:USM/JEPeM/16040170) and National Medical Research Register, Malaysia Ministry of Health (NMRR-16-2172-32981(IIR)).

Instruments

Perceptions of stigma were measured using the Malay Version of Devaluation-Discrimination Scale (DDS) which was translated and validated for local use¹⁶. It has high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha 0.85), almost similar with the original DDS (Cronbach's alpha of 0.88) (3). The DDS (Malay Version) is a 12-items self-rated tool to assess the degree of beliefs that person will devalue or discriminate against individual with mental illness. This scale is a 4-point Likert Scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 4 (strongly disagree). The items 5, 6, 7, 9, 11 and 12 were reversely scored. Then, all item scores were summed and divided by 12 to get the mean score of perceived stigma score.

The Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale-Extended version (BPRS-E) is an expanded version of BPRS with 5-components and 24-items. The internal consistencies (Cronbach's alpha) of the components were acceptable to good, with the exception of disorientation(positive symptoms: 0.74; depression: 0.75; negative symptoms: 0.76; mania 0.64 and disorientation: 0.55)²⁴. The symptoms were rated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (not present) to 7 (extremely severe) from a 15 to 30 minutes interview. The higher the score indicates the more severe psychopathology.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS version 24.0 was used for data entry and analysis. Univariate analysis (independent T-test) was conducted to compare the mean stigma score between the two groups. To measure the predictive factors, simple and multiple linear regressions were used.

Table 2. Distribution of perceived stigma score based on each item of DDS-M among the patients with schizophrenia (n = 140)

Items	Mean (SD)	n (%)			
		Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Most people would accept a person who once had a serious mental illness as a close friend.	2.75(.711)	15(10.7)	82(58.6)	36(25.7)	7(5.0)
2. Most people believe that a person who has been in a psychiatric hospital is just as intelligent as the average citizen.	2.41(.748)	8(5.7)	55(39.3)	63(45)	14(10)
3. Most people believe that a person who has been hospitalized for serious mental illness as a teacher.	2.73(.812)	19(13.6)	77(55.0)	31(22.1)	13(9.3)
4. Most people would accept a person who has made a full recovery serious mental illness as a teacher of a young children in public school.	2.61(.870)	20(14.3)	62(44.3)	42(30)	16(11.4)
5. Most people believe that entering a psychiatric hospital is a sign of personal failure (R)	2.66(.784)	10(7.1)	45(32.1)	68(48.6)	17(12.1)
6. Most people will not hire a person who has been hospitalized for serious mental illness to take care of their children, even if he or she had been well for some time. (R)	2.59(.872)	18(12.9)	39(27.9)	65(46.4)	18(12.9)
7. Most people think less of a person who has been in a psychiatric hospital. (R)	2.57(.760)	11(7.9)	50(35.7)	67(47.9)	12(8.6)
8. Most employers will hire a person who has been hospitalized.	2.89(.727)	22(15.7)	89(63.6)	21(15)	8(5.7)
9. Most employers will pass over the application of a person who has been hospitalized for mental illness in favor of another applicant. (R)	2.30(.737)	13(9.3)	82(58.6)	35(25)	10(7.1)
10. Most people in my community would treat a person who has been hospitalized for mental illness just as they would treat anyone.	2.66(.828)	19(13.6)	68(48.6)	40(28.6)	13(9.3)
11. Most young women would be reluctant to date a man who has been hospitalized for a serious mental illness. (R)	2.34(.829)	21(15)	61(43.6)	47(33.6)	11(7.9)
12. Once they know a person was in a psychiatric hospital, most people will take his or her opinion less seriously. (R)	2.27(.776)	20(14.3)	70(50)	42(30)	8(5.7)

DDS- Devaluation Discrimination Scale (4-points, strongly agree = 1 to strongly disagree = 4) "R"-indicate reverse scoring

RESULTS

Characteristics of the Participants

The sociodemographic characteristics of participants are shown in Table 1. The mean age of 140 participants is 37.95 (SD, 10.79). Male (n = 79, 56.4%) is more than female with majority is Malay (n = 138, 98.6%). Most of them is single (n = 105, 75%), received secondary education (n = 97, 69.3%), and not working or housewife (n = 98, 70%). Almost all of them have been diagnosed with schizophrenia for more than one year (n = 127, 90.7%) (Table 1).

The distribution of perceived stigma scores based on each item of DDS-M among the participants (n = 140) is shown in Table 2. The mean scores for items ranged from 2.27(SD.776) to 2.89 (SD.727).

The mean score of perceived stigma in schizophrenia patients who attended psychosocial rehabilitation was 2.40 (SD = 0.39) and in those who did not attend it was 2.73 (SD = 0.39). The mean difference score of perceived stigma between two groups was .335 (95% CI .204, .465) with p value < 0.001(Table 3).

Each of the independent variables was analysed using simple linear regression (SLR) to determine the predictive factors between socio-demographic and clinical variables with the level of perceived stigma measured by the DDS-M. Socio-demographic factors that were significantly associated with perceived stigma were age (p < 0.05) were race (p < 0.001). Somatic concern (p < 0.001), anxiety (p < 0.05), depression (p < 0.001), guilt (p < 0.05), elevated mood (p < 0.05), suspiciousness (p < 0.05), and hallucinations (p < 0.05) were psychopathology symptoms measured by BPRS-E, significantly associated with level of perceived stigma. Other variables with p-value < 0.25 or clinically important were also selected for multivariable analysis.

The analysis was continued with the multiple linear regression (MLR) analysis. MLR would be the control for confounding effects among the clinical and statistical significant variable. Twenty two variables that met the initial screening criteria (p < 0.25) were entered into the MLR. Those variables were entered backward, forward and stepwise into the MLR. The only significant socio-demographic factor was ethnic (p < .005), while clinical factors were somatic concern (p < .05) and

depression (p < .001). Results were considered significant at p < 0.05 (please refer Table 4).

DISCUSSION

Malay is the largest population in Kelantan as reflected by the percentage of the participants (98.6%). There was a significant negative association between ethnic and perceived stigma. It can be concluded that the Malay is associated with low perceived stigma. In Kelantan, Islam is the religion for almost all of the Malays. This association may also reflect that Muslim people have negative relationship with perceived stigma.

Anglin *et al* carried out a telephone survey among households and exhibited that there were racial differences among African Americans and Caucasians public²⁵. The culture in certain ethnic or community attributes to the way of perception or belief towards mental illness. Asian community, especially the Malay tend to keep things to themselves and hardly express their feelings. Malay Muslims view the symptoms or the manifestations of the mental illness as emotional disturbances rather than as mental disorder. Thus, they perceived them as normal²⁶.

This finding is almost similar with a study that stated people following Islam religion have lesser stigma against mental illness²⁷. Some Muslims may perceive mental illness as a trial and means of purifying oneself²⁸. Mental illness also can be a way to relink with Allah and further strengthen one's faith²⁹.

American Muslims perceive that the way of healing is through prayer, recitation of the Quran and Islamic spiritual leaders³⁰. A fundamental belief of Islam is that there is only one God which is Allah and Allah causes everything including illnesses²⁷. A Muslim believes that Allah knows what the best is for them and they accept whatever happens to them. Thus, this concept reduces the perceived stigma among Muslim, consistent with the findings among Thai Muslim community³¹.

However, there is also a strong perception that mental illness is caused by supernatural powers, such as Jinn. Therefore, a person may decide to visit religious or traditional healers instead of mental health professionals³². This may lead to a barrier to mental health services and prolong the duration of untreated psychosis.

Table 3. Comparison of mean score perceived stigma between psychosocial rehabilitation and without psychosocial rehabilitation

Variable	Mean (SD)		Mean difference (95% CI)	t statistic (df)	p value *
	Psychosocial Rehabilitation	No Psychosocial Rehabilitation			
Mean score	2.40 (.39)	2.73 (.39)	.335 (.204, .465)	5.064	< 0.001

*Independent t-test

Table 4. Simple and multiple linear regression analysis of socio-demographic and clinical factors with level of perceived stigma

Variable	SLR				MLR			
	b (95% CI)	T stat	p-value	R ²	b (95% CI)	T stat	p value	
Ethnicity	-.682 (-1.043, -.321)	-3.734	.000	.092	-.488 (-.808,-.168)	-3.016	.003	
Somatic Concern	-.156 (-.230, -.081)	-4.128	.000	.332	-.088 (-.166,-.010)	-2.245	.026	
Depression	-.234 (-.310, -.157)	-6.035	.000	.209	-.176 (-.258,-.093)	-4.214	.000	

Simple linear regression (outcome as mean stigma score)

^aCrude regression coefficient,^cMultiple Linear Regression (There is no significant interaction; no multi collinearity problem; and linearity, normality and equal variance assumptions were made)^dAdjusted regression coefficientR² = 0.325

This study exhibits a significant association between somatic concern and depression with perceived stigma. The association of perceived stigma and depression has also been proved in other studies^{33,34}. The more severe of depression is, the stronger predictor of perceived stigma³⁵. In a qualitative study; anger, depression, fear and anxiety are among the common impacts of stigma and obstacle from recovery or help seeking behaviour³⁶.

However, this study showed those who were more depressed and had somatic concern, the less perceived stigma they had. The possible explanation is the way they perceived the depression and somatic as part of the emotional or anxiety symptoms that were normal²⁶. Thus, they did not look at it as part of mental illness.

The significant mean difference (.335 (95% CI .204, .465.) p < 0.001) of perceived stigma score between two groups of schizophrenia patients in this study reflects that the psychosocial rehabilitation decreases the perceived stigma. This outcome verifies that psychosocial rehabilitation is important in reducing perceived stigma among schizophrenia patients.

Among psychosocial rehabilitation interventions include psychoeducation, social skills training, group therapy, vocational training and others. Those activities will lead to an increased self-esteem and proper understanding about schizophrenia. The journey to recovery will be hastened and finally achieved.

The importance of psychosocial rehabilitation needs to be emphasized to the patients and their family members. Other study also showed that a person with mental illness has found that involvement in self-help groups and advocacy organizations was helpful in coping with stigma^{15,5}. Involvement of family members is the most crucial as they need to take the patient regularly to the psychosocial rehabilitation centre and show to the patients how much they support the patients. Hence, enthusiastic, skilled and well trained mental health staff is another core element in making the psychosocial rehabilitation intervention beneficial to the patient and the family members.

Nevertheless, there are some limitations in this study. First, it was done in Kelantan where most of the population are Malays, therefore it could not be generalised to the whole Malaysia. Studies that involve most of the sites and race of Malaysia should be carried out in the future. This cross-sectional study is unable to see the causal relationship between the associated factors and perceived stigma. Therefore, a proper study to see the causal relationship needs to be done. A qualitative study with in-depth interviews might be able to understand the cultural differences and view of perceived stigma in Malaysia properly.

CONCLUSIONS

Ethnic, somatic concern and depression were the significant predictive factors for stigma in schizophrenia patients. Psychosocial rehabilitation significantly reduced perceived stigma among patients with schizophrenia. Thus, patients with schizophrenia should receive psychosocial rehabilitation and the predictive factors should be considered as part of the holistic management of schizophrenia towards recovery.

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